

Architecture and Seduction

The Structure in the Hyperstructure

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Introduction

Richard Strauss's scandalous opera *Salome* opened in May 1906 in Graz, Austria. The audience famously included Gustav Mahler, Giacomo Puccini, Arnold Schönberg, Alban Berg, Alexander von Zemlinsky, and adolescent Adolf Hitler (Ross 2019). Based on Oscar Wilde's play, the libretto, already on trial nine years earlier for indecency and blasphemy, became equally controversial and thus banned in Vienna, New York, and London.

The adaptation continued to be a scandal, mainly because of Salome's erotic and ambiguous Dance, a tale first emerging in the Bible. Hidden in the early scriptures, her name appears in Jewish Antiquities (18.5.4), followed by mentions in Mark:16-29 and Matt 14:8.

In all narratives, the young princess gets asked to dance for her stepfather, King Herod, and his guests. In exchange, she can ask for anything in return. Her request is the head of St. John the Baptist. A vulgar act, concluded by the death of a Christian prophet and exhibited as an ancient cautionary tale. The censorship of her murderous seduction circles through millennia. Over 100 instruments are essential in Strauss's opera, though only occasionally reaching their total capacity.

The subtle and light performance takes form of a scherzo, which indicates, in musical context, a playful piece that is light-hearted and fast-paced (Kennedy n.d.).

This research aligns with Strauss's announcement during an early rehearsal:

“Gentlemen, there are no difficulties or problems. This is a *scherzo with a fatal conclusion*” (Ross 2019).

The following study explores the intersections of architectural theory and practice by employing a qualitative research methodology. It is laid out in three main chapters, each launched by an anecdote from the opera Salome.

The Veil has been lifted, interprets contemporary architecture within the character of its epoch. The theoretical frameworks of Hyper-reality, Ideology, and Simulacra shaped by French philosopher and sociologist Jean Baudrillard (1929-2007) are initially introduced and connected with related philosophical concepts, literature, and architectural case studies.

Baudrillard's oeuvre continues throughout the research, as his publications on simulation, seduction, and the fatal, catalyzed the initial outline for the paper.

The second chapter, *The Dance of the Seven Veils*, establishes Seduction as a design strategy and a potential response to the aforementioned contemporary context. The attributes of *Seduction* are concentrated into seven categories: *Distance, Deception, Indifference, Enigma, Ceremony, Play, and Power*. A spatial rhetoric is formed by the theoretical analysis of selected philosophical texts and thematic literature reviews that are compared and supported by the examination of case studies, which were chosen for their relevance to the reviewed theoretical frameworks and analyzed to uncover connected insights and patterns. The case studies' data was collected from various sources and varies in the inclusion of plans, historical contexts and site visits.

The ethical dimension and fatality of an Architecture of Seduction is addressed in the third chapter, *Scherzo with a Fatal Conclusion*. The moral implications in spatial applications are explored by analogizing traditional ethical theories in philosophy, architectural theories, and trending themes of past Venice Architecture Biennali. The findings connect relevant interdisciplinary concepts with practical architectural applications, synthesizing the first chapter's critical cultural depiction and the second chapter's offered architectural solutions.

The subchapter Fatal Phenomenology positions the connotations of the triumphal building-as-object by implementing literature reviews and concluding the research by undermining the validity of an autarkic architecture while simultaneously setting into a contemporary architectural discourse.

This research aims to identify the parameters and evaluate a strategy in relationship to previous and ongoing narratives while reframing mechanisms of seduction inside a spatial order.

How does Seduction manifest in architecture?

Fig.1

THE VEIL HAS BEEN LIFTED

*THE YOUNG SYRIAN:
HOW BEAUTIFUL IS THE PRINCESS SALOME TONIGHT!*

*THE PAGE OF HERODIAS:
YOU ARE ALWAYS LOOKING AT HER. YOU LOOK AT HER TOO MUCH. IT
IS DANGEROUS TO LOOK AT PEOPLE IN SUCH FASHION. SOMETHING
TERRIBLE MAY HAPPEN.*

(WILDE 1967)

The Hyperstructure

*“We do not believe that the truth remains true
once the veil has been lifted” Nietzsche*

Categorizing contemporary architecture into a cohesive aesthetic and narrative framework is seemingly impossible. Architectural styles are no longer mapped out by their location and time, a predicament that can be traced back to the invention of perspective (lat. clear-seeing) in the Renaissance and the global paradigm shift emerging from the Industrial Revolution, followed by today's digital information age. With the development of perspective, the modern notion of individualism was born, corresponding directly between representation and “the unique point of view of the individual spectator” (Giedion 1982, 31). Five centuries later, the aftermath of the two world wars led to a sober and pragmatic approach to representation in architecture, a radical and gradually globally mimicked transition, urging for a material truth. “Reality (...) was indexed against illusion, dreams, art, magic” (Baudrillard 1990, 13).

Modernism formed the framework of its deconstruction by provoking the following period of postmodernism, patterned by having an end purpose in itself. Jean-Francois Lyotard marked the postmodern condition as the end of master narratives (such as the march of reason, wealth accumulation, technological advancements, worker emancipation, and so on), which in modernity had appeared synonymous with progress (Hal 1996, 205).

The digital age generated an “inferno of the same” (Han 2017, 8) and “unlimited possibility” (Han 2017, 1) globalism. Resembling Richard Wagner's *Flying Dutchman*, contemporary culture restlessly floats without aim. Post-history, post-truth, deriving from what we had inadvertently collectively asked for, we have reached a “crisis of achieved utopia” (Baudrillard 1990, 8).

On account of the current zeitgeist, our society is charged by a conceptual emptiness filled with self-referential ideologies “a symptom of increasing critical consciousness in a world that has lost its condence in ultimate truths” (Lawson 1985). The globalizing tendency in which everything is decentered and hence centered, the center is consequently lost and invalid, a bubble in foam (Sloterdijk 2011, 66).

Althusser argues that “ideology has a material existence,” representing “the imaginary relationship of individuals to their real conditions (...)” (Althusser 2001, 108). Therefore, it is not a secluded phenomenon occurring only in the mind, nor a superstructure, but instead subtly embedded in the always present forces of our practices, a buoyant thing.

Franz Kafka’s novel *The Trial* is a surreal parade of hidden totalitarian authority and its dysfunctional, absurd patterns. The depicted bureaucratic surveillance is undeniably present but never directly revealed. The protagonist is caught in a veiled modern panopticon, doomed by ideological anamorphosis. Against interpretation, ideology functions as a “generative matrix that regulates the relationship between visible and non-visible, between imaginable and non-imaginable, as well as the changes in this relationship” (Žižek 1994, 1). Therefore, it is, by definition, self-referential, inherently initiating itself by forming a distance to mere ideology.

“The matrix is the type of movie the matrix would have made about the matrix” (Baudrillard 1990, 8).

Our present-day reality is devoured by its own exaggeration, “just as sex disappears in porn, and events in the news” (Baudrillard 1990, 13), the classical divisions disappear because of their thorough negotiation. “(...) (T)hings are obscene (specifically because) they have too much meaning (and) thus attain an exorbitant representation of the truth.” (Baudrillard 1990, 81) and finality.

Jean Baudrillard identified this phenomenon as *Simulacra*, a condition that can be traced back to Plato’s writings on sculpture. A naturalistic sculpture made to look real is a simulation. A sculpture of a bigger scale, placed on a column, counterbalances its new perspective by enlarging parts of the upper body, canceling out any parallaxical errors of proportion. Viewed linearly, the physical distribution appears false; however, the body looks real from the ground on account of the artificial render of the sculpture.

This is the simulacrum. The representations are not opposites to existence; on the contrary, they become their own reality.

The Structure

The *hyper-structure* (architectural matters) is imminently embedded into the *hyper-object* (architectural matter).

Reaching the endpoint of modernity, or postmodernity, we have exceeded it (Breitschmitt, 2019) and entered a *hyper-reality*, which becomes evident in the Trompe L`Oeil (trick the eye) (Fig.2). The two-dimensionality of the studio is “falsar than false—the secret of appearances” (Baudrillard 1991, 25) and, consequently, due to the low level of representation and lack of perspective, too much reality.

Giuseppe Terragni’s *Casa del Fascio* (House of Fascism) is a modern glass-house, following the Mussolinian concept that “Fascism is a glass house into which everyone can peer” (Schnapp 2008, 46) transparently, directly replacing all meaning and myth with symbols and signs, it disappears in the hyperbole of reality (Fig.4). The cover of the tenth issue of *Il Vetro* (Fig.5) illustrates this moment of Italian modernity. A *Balilla* (fascist boy scout) is captured behind a panel of tempered glass; the viewer’s gaze can peer through the material, but the image is opaque. This is the hyper-real, as “(it) is not an illusion. It is not a false world of Platonic cave shadows, from which one could escape. It is the more real than real” (Baudrillard 1990, 13). The boy in uniform is not shown in a pronounced pose á la Riefenstahl, nor is he hidden, making his blurry depiction more direct than direct.

Renzo Piano and Richard Rogers’ inside-out *Centre Pompidou* (Fig.3) operates subversively in the hyper-real milieu. Modernist functional concerns were materialized and replaced by technical transparency. Expressing larger societal problems, it reaches the pure hyper-object, inaugurating a hyper-structural era in which architecture, body, and fashion turned political and empowering. Things had found a way to react to the threat that was “(...) not passivity but pseudo-activity, the urge to “be active,” to “participate,” to mask the Nothingness of what goes on” (Zizek 2006, 334), a culturization turning architecture into an event. As a consequence of this “indifferentiation into an analytical and ideological fog” (Baudrillard 1990, 82), the new credo no longer existed in the formal but in the symbolic as a total simulacra embedded in a hyper-reality (Baudrillard 1981); the Beaubourgian hyper-truth.

A manifestation of “the irruption of the obscene: the end of the secret - the irruption of transparency” (Baudrillard 1990, 45).

It is the inverse of finalities: the hysteria of casualty, “corresponding to the simultaneous erasure of origins and causes: the obsessive search for origin, responsibility, and reference - an attempt to exhaust phenomena back to their infinitesimal causes” (Baudrillard 1990, 31) that has triggered a romanticization of a pre-simulation “Real” place.

“What precautions should we have taken to avoid this historical collapse, this coma, this volatilization of the real? Did we commit some error?” (Baudrillard 1990, 34)

Fig.2

Fig.3

Fig.4

Fig.5

Fig.6

DANCE OF THE SEVEN VEILS

HEROD:

*I WILL NOT GO WITHIN TILL SHE HATH DANCED. DANCE, SALOME,
DANCE FOR ME.*

HERODIAS:

DO NOT DANCE, MY DAUGHTER.

SALOME

I AM READY, TETRARCH.

[SALOME DANCES THE DANCE OF THE SEVEN VEILS.]

(WILDE 1967)

Seducing the void

*The world is naked, the king is naked, and things are clear.
All of production, and truth itself, are directed towards disclosure, the unbearable
“truth” of sex being but the most recent consequence. Luckily, at bottom, there is nothing to it. And seduction still holds, in the face of truth, a most sibylline response, which is that “perhaps we wish to uncover the truth because it is so difficult to imagine it naked.” (Baudrillard 1991, 181)*

Baudrillard’s cynical depiction of reality raises the question of whether we can overcome this blur, and should. The simulacra exhibit the absence of any veiled authenticity and truth; therefore, the simulation is not in opposition to reality but rather in unity. It is only the altered truth we can live with in conformity; “otherwise life becomes unbearable (precisely because the truth does not exist)” (Baudrillard 1991, 59). Adding meaning to things in order to counterbalance the repercussions of a historical collapse produces an obscene condition by taking up too much space and thus attaining too much truth, which only manufactures an apogee of the simulacrum (Baudrillard 1990, 81).

Sloterdijk argues that for an object of truth, the subject needs to disappear. Hence, unless we are willing to die for truth, there will be no truth anymore—a final alternative to the simulacra. “(T)he violence of the symbolic - the obligation to reciprocate on levels deeper than objects” (Baudrillard 1990, 12) is haunting since we can not fully reach this void.

However, if the void is prudent, we must learn to seduce it.

Seduction (lat. to lead away, dt. ver-führung) “takes from discourse its sense and turns it from its truth” ((Baudrillard 1990, 58); it attracts signs instead of contradicting them and tears the same away from the same. Against the terror of a *modus vivendi*, truer-than-true, falser-than-false, deader-than-dead, livelier-than-life, seduction turns vulgarly im-mortal prospects towards sovereignty. It “abuses signs and subjects” (Baudrillard 1990, 75), makes them lose meaning, and masters their appearance. It is a cynical response to a cynical condition, a surface approach arguing for great lies between bland lies.

*A tactic, not an end in itself.
Not God but the church.*

Seven Attributes of Seduction

Seduction resists the idea of taking a single form. It prioritizes the persuasion of signs over the emergence of any truth “-which interpretation neglects and destroys in its search for hidden meanings” (Baudrillard 1990, 53); therefore, any interpretation is par excellence opposed to seduction.

Hence, the architecture of seduction is *against clarification*.

Fig.7

Dis-tanz

Distance is a space between two points. Seduction animates this gap, initiating a *dis-tanz*, a dance. Han states that “(e)rotic desire is tied to a particular absence of the other - not the absence of nothingness but rather absence in a horizon of the future” (Han 2017, 15). It is an in-between space, from-to, and therefore, always relational and movable.

In the *Genealogy of Morals*, Nietzsche reminds us of the historical cultivation of a “pathos of distance” as a signifier of nobility and differentiation, ultimately leading to a Will. Baudrillard adds that “(b)y the abolition of distance, of the ‘pathos’ of distance, everything becomes undecidable.” (Baudrillard 2005).

Distance is thus attached to human desire; hence, it is a mental construct that is only created when we want something to be closer or farther away.

Jean Nouvel’s monolith for the Expo 02 in Morat, Switzerland, is a container for art (Fig. 7). Placed in the middle of Lake Murten, the structure re-composites the existing landscape by adding an ambiguous 23-meter wide and 7-meter high object into the distance. Visitors were taken to the cube by a small ferry, which, once entered, revealed a 360° curved screen, rhythmically projecting digital images. The three-story pavilion allowed for the visitor to experience the exhibition in individual order. Nouvel’s volume fascinates in particular because of its placement. It seems unattainable and isolated and is not easily accessible.

The object thus becomes a real and imaginary distant container of desire, seducing by a suggestion.

It is a woman whispering into the man’s ear, “What are you doing after the orgy?” It is a potential rendezvous, an occasion to look forward to and build toward a slight shift in perspective, which creates a more promising view of the orgy itself (Baudrillard 1910, 10).

Fig.7

Fig.8

Deception

In Cristóbal Balenciaga's (1895-1972) days, commonly known as Monsieur and founder of the *House of Balenciaga*, the house at 10th Avenue George V in Paris hosted aspirational couture with a French neoclassical backdrop.

"He only played up his background on rare occasions, adding to runway shows a bolero jacket or sailor blouse here, a flamenco skirt or infanta dress there, and to his Parisian salon a thick curlicue motif in white-on-white stucco. The arabesques arched over white duchesse-curtained window recesses, around mirrors and doorways, and the silhouettes of settees." (Stagg n.d)

Fifty-two years after its closure, artistic director Demna Gvasalia and Berlin-based firm Sub renovated and reopened the salon (Fig.8,9). The new design is faithful, serving as a time capsule, replicating the interior details (Fig. 10-12). The renovation included white stucco arabesques, patinated light gray carpets, artificial dust, and curtains with the effects of ash stain. The ground floor facade offers a harsh contrast by including pneumatic vitrines with darkened glass, hiding and protecting the garments (Chodha 2024). The created illusion of timelessness and perfection through imperfection *veils and unveils* the past.

"Occasionally words must serve to veil the facts," argues Machiavelli in his instructions to diplomat Raffaello Girolami. He believes we need to be more than ourselves, or at least appear as so.

In the ancient Greek tale, Narcissus mistakes his face mirrored in the water for another. The surface he is looking at can not be depicted independently. As it depends on the subject, it is mythical by abolishing the difference between the same and the other. 'I'll be your mirror' does not signify 'I'll be your reflection' but 'I'll be your deception'.

The apparent misperception of reality produces only objects or real signs and powerfully returns reality to its fundamental illusion (Baudrillard 1991, 69). It is not false; its signs point nowhere. Deception disappoints the demand for meaning and destabilizes captivatingly (Baudrillard 1990, 75).

Fig.9

Fig. 10

Fig.11

Fig.12

Fig.13

Indifference

Baudrillard presents in *Fatal Strategies* that only the subject can desire and only the object can seduce (Baudrillard 1990). In other words, *things dominate* since they do not and can not desire and, therefore, are not seduced.

This subject-object relationship is not equal since the desiring subject is at the mercy of its own seduction. The seductress/object does not attach meaning or suffers the weight of desire. It is indifferent. And consequently, because of its indifference and ambivalence, it is fatally seductive. The object takes away from the subject's desire, who has no say in this, and turns to newness.

Valerio Olgiati argues for architectural aspects of newness and ambivalence, which he refers to as *Non-referential*. An approach devoid of outside symbolic, cultural, and historical contexts. (Breitschmid 2019).

His auditorium in Landquart, Switzerland, follows this logic (Fig.13).

It is a multifunctional hall, with a roof pitching sharply from a low-rise entrance towards its three times higher concrete wall. The solid construction is combined with a timber frame system, stretching in the interior.

It is indifferent to its context and presumptions and, therefore, seductive by its objective lack of concern.

During an interview in the magazine *LOG59*, Peter Eisenmann and Valerio Olgiati argue about the notions of sense. Eisenmann reveals that he is working on a similar theme, the *becoming unmotivated of the sign*, a self-referential approach, empty of meaning and focused on the index of buildings.

They divert on the issue of 'sense,' as Eisenmann seems to question its relevance in design, while Olgiati insists on it. In seduction, objects are allowed to be senseless signs, as they are inherently pure and fatal.

Ex Nihilo.

Fig.14

Enigma

The Seducer's Diary by Søren Kierkegaard depicts the plotted seduction of the young woman Cordelia. Originally published under the pseudonym Johannes Climacus, Kierkegaard depicts the relentless strategic pursuit of seduction, bordering on sincerity and deception. Cordelia is idealized and thus becomes the enigma to be solved. To seduce her, Johannes turns himself into an enigma, launching an enigmatic duel that can be only solved by seduction (Kierkegaard 1987). The enigma's secret is not revealed, as, consequently, sexuality would become transparent. Words point to nothing; meaning does not occur, and the secret of seduction moves faster than its sense.

Beneath the discourse, seduction is the "secret circulation" (Baudrillard 1991, 80) that touches you before the sentences arrive.

The universal occurrence of enigmas in the form of myths allows culture to appear distorted, not hidden. The modern detachment from such masquerades, in the form of demystification and denunciation, has become its own discourse and declaration, burying intentions below stocks of phrases (Barthes 1977, 166). Baudrillard argues that if the world is enigmatic, we should not try to make it more truthful but rather render it more obscure. It is the echoing of the invisible that seduces.

Renato Rizzi approaches the secret in his project of the Villaricca, located in Napoli. Challenging the dual conditions of modernity in the city, Rizzi expresses the echoing gap, firstly preserved in the dungeons and secondly sedimented on the surface. The project *La pupilla di Partenope* (Fig. 14-16), the eye of the Greek siren, is characterized by two conditions: the invisible image on the horizontal plane and the image of the gorgo on the vertical plane. As it sinks into the ground, sucking the veins of the earth, the structure creates a void in the center to make the eye float. Above only the sky, below all the possible connections, a round plan with a center room (diameter 40m) is wrapped by four layers: horizontal distribution, vertical distribution, service distribution, and a ramp system. Each level of the section connects with an independent system of linear paths penetrating the urban fabric of Villaricca. As the mythical constellation of tunnels, crevices, caves, and cisterns enters the foundations of Napoli, the aforementioned secret circulation of seduction transpires. Against modernity, the city expands its enigma.

Fig.15

Fig.16

“We will find subtle forms of radicalizing secret qualities; we will fight obscenity with its own weapons. To the truer than true we will oppose the falsier than false. We will not oppose the beautiful to the ugly, but will look for the uglier than ugly: the monstrous. We will not oppose the visible to the hidden, but will look for the more hidden than hidden: the secret.” (Baudrillard 1991, 25)

Fig.17

Ceremony

John Pawson's museum for *The Feuerle Collection* is located in a 6500 sqm bunker in Kreuzberg, Berlin (Fig. 17-19). Built in 1942, the original telecommunications base is characterized by its 2 and 3.5-meter thick concrete walls and ceiling. Pawson's design for the collection is subtle; the previous bomb shield is transformed into an entrance leading to the basement, where one enters the sound room. The absence of natural light and carefully placed spotlights in the exhibition space is introduced by a spatial initiation of darkness, readjusting the senses to the room's atmosphere. During the construction period, flooding problems were triggered by the neighboring canal. The accident resulted in a 2000 sqm Lake Room, preserved due to Pawson's modest approach. The surfaces were recovered by removing the plaster, dirt, and graffiti from the columns. The basement's Incense Room is elevated on a platform featuring two-way mirrors. The focus lies on the peace of the ceremonial room whilst keeping a relationship to the outside space.

“Provocation - unlike seduction, which allows things to come into play and appear in secret, dual and ambiguous - does not leave you free to be; it calls on you to reveal yourself as you are” (Baudrillard 1991, 61). John Pawson's design strategy is not a polemic gesture, which would be obscene and, therefore, not seductive. It is a ritualistic ceremony rather than a provocation of the building's historical dimension.

According to Baudrillard, we never desire the real event but its *spectacle*. It is not things but their signs, a perversion that causes us not to want things to actually change, but wanting the change to seduce us (Baudrillard 1991, 102).

Ceremonies are intertwined with the concept of distance, as they remove the external distance of the participants through a shared experience while substituting this shift by the creation of an internal distance of the participants through imagery-provoked fantasies (Hal 1996, 220)

Christo and Jeanne-Claude's wrapped Reichstag was such a seductive spectacle (Fig. 20). One hundred thousand sqm of thick woven polypropylene fabric were wrapped around the facade. The building's ambivalent symbol in the history of German democracy was not deconstructed by a riot of the artists. As Rivarol says: “The people didn't really want a Revolution, they wanted a spectacle of it” (Baudrillard 1991, 102).

Fig.18

Fig.19

Fig.20

Fig.21

Play

In the *Tales of 1001 Nights*, Sherezeade tells stories to save her life. After an incident of unfaithfulness, Sharyar, the king, decides to marry a new woman each day, only to kill her the next morning. Sherezeade, caught in the king's deadly boudoir, begins to tell him a story, but as the night passes and dawn breaks in, she stops in the middle. The king begs her to finish; however, it is late. Setting fiction against death, she discontinues the narrative, leaves a gap, and survives to finish the story another night.

Sherezeade seduces the king by a play of appearance. It is not the appearance of the tales but their disappearances at the right moment that lead her to survive. "Absence here seduces presence" (Baudrillard 1990, 85) not by pure absence but by the eclipse of a presence. Her strategy becomes hypnotic.

Baudrillard argues that seduction is not linked to affects but to the fragility of appearance. It is based on a pact, a challenge, which is not a universal and natural form but an artificially initiated one. The genius of appearance is hence a perversion (Baudrillard 1991, 130), operating in accord with a secret rule of the moment of seduction, the suspension of seduction, the risk of seduction, the accident of seduction, the delirium of seduction, and the pause of seduction (Baudrillard 1991, 84).

During the years of 1958-1974, Carlo Scarpa carefully restored the *Castelvecchio Museum* (Fig.21-28). Located in Verona, Italy, the project stands out due to its mastery of detail. In a lecture about the process, Scarpa declared, "Castelvecchio was all fake." Proclaiming the building's falsity, he began his intervention, a theatrical scenography. Beams indicate paths; some are left protruding. Displaying the sculptures on pedestals and designing all central supports, the artifacts seem to be levitating. There are no repetitive patterns, the lighting is 'low-tech', and the floor is divided by carpets out of stone. The surfaces are undisrupted since all installation is carefully hidden.

Scarpa artificially cuts into in-between spaces and connects them back by bridges; he cuts into walls and leaves a slit. It is a dialogue between old and new, light and shadow, appearance and disappearance, a play. Carlo Scarpa disjoints and connects the narrative with a '*sherezeadian*' genius and sensibility.

Fig.22

Fig.23

Fig.24

Fig.25

Fig.26

Fig.27

Fig.28

Fig.29

Power

In 1962, Minoru Yamasaki was appointed to commission the *World Trade Center* (Fig. 29-31). He did not believe in the validity of strength as a precondition for good architecture and prioritized not how the building met the sky but how it met the ground. Four years later, the New York Times architecture critic Huxtable wrote of the towers, “Here we have the world’s daintiest architecture for the world’s biggest buildings.” The span between the columns was ridiculed for being too dainty, though the buildings were structurally strong. The layout was designed to erase the floors of columns; alternatively, the towers were supported by steel tubes and stiffened by exterior columns. The steel columns at the core of the building carried the remaining loads, supported by steel trusses spanning the outer and inner tubes. (Lange 2021). The high-rising mirrored sculptures became an urban symbol, embodying the simulation by erecting a doubled vertigo that dominated New York’s skyline. The twins symbolized for Baudrillard the perfect embodiment of today’s “definitive world order/power”; their duplication framed a lack of reference. The collapse of the Twin Towers reordered the structures into the imaginary space, now revealed in the presence of their absence. “Even in their pulverized state... No one who knew them can cease imagining them ... Their end in material space has borne them off into a definite imaginary space...” (Baudrillard 2003, 36-37).

The notion of power and weakness in seduction is depicted in the multi-faceted aspects of the towers. “To seduce is to appear weak. To seduce is to render weak. We seduce with our weakness, never with strong signs or powers” (Baudrillard 1991, 83). Yamasaki’s thin columns appeared fragile, which supplied the buildings with seductive qualities. As previously stated, seduction represents mastery over the symbolic universe, while power represents only mastery of the real universe (Guignion 2018).

Thus, seduction is stronger than power due to its reversibility and mortality. Power partakes in all of the illusions of the real since it wants to be real, therefore becoming its own imaginary. “Power, whatever it is and wherever it comes from, is a symbolic murder, and it must be expiated by murder” (Baudrillard 1990, 105). Seduction, denying things their truth, turns to the pure power play of appearances, which is consequently the authority over all systems of power. Power, if it really wants to be effective in its continuity, should desire its own death, as it leads to the imaginary sphere—*a fatal destiny*.

Fig.30

Fig. 31

Fig.32

A SCHERZO WITH A FINAL CONCLUSION

HEROD:

AH! WONDERFUL! WONDERFUL! YOU SEE THAT SHE HAS DANCED FOR ME, YOUR DAUGHTER. COME NEAR, SALOME, COME NEAR, THAT I MAY GIVE THEE THY REWARD. AH! I PAY THE DANCERS WELL. I WILL PAY THEE ROYALLY. I WILL GIVE THEE WHATSOEVER THY SOUL DESIRETH. WHAT WOULDST THOU HAVE? SPEAK.

SALOME:

[RISING.] THE HEAD OF IOKANAAN.

Beyond Truth and Evil

In *Architecture Depends*, Jeremy Till criticizes the usage of the terms ethics and morals in architecture and separates them into four common usages. Ethics originary sense ethos is the articulation of a commonly agreed custom that human beings have agreed upon. The secondary meaning derived from Aristotle is associated with the evolution of the good self in the pursuit of good conduct. The Kantian sense of ethics integrates a universal code of morals into a wider project of reason. The utilitarian interpretation is the arrangement of knowledge to generate the highest benefits for the highest number of people. Till argues that an architectural execution under the framework of the previous guises smothers the possibility and otherness of the world, given that they assume a definite good (Till 2009,173).

Baudrillard critiques this enduring trend of *Moral Theory*, proclaiming that seduction, going inherently beyond reality and illusion, goes past the Moral Theory (Vaughan 2010, 55). The *Ethics of Seduction* is an extreme form of *Moral Skepticism*, evaluating right or wrong in terms of their attractiveness rather than distinctiveness (Gane 1991, 147). The dual attraction of opposites, of 'black' or 'white,' of good or evil, provokes their mutual seduction into a moral 'gray' (Gane 1991, 148).

The 2000 Venice Architecture Biennale, "*Less Aesthetics, More Ethics*," urged designers to go beyond appearance and style. The proposed rebalance of priorities was flawed, suggesting that "if you just play down aesthetic excess, then ethics will emerge in the gaps that are left" (Till 2009, 174). It marked the rise of what Byung-Chul Han identifies as a "society of positivity from which negativity has disappeared (,) one of bare life (...) a slave's life" (Han 2017, P25). Charging life with the positive and death with the negative is a modern desire; it mocks the universal collusiveness of inseparable forms. The Kantian subject is thus not equipped to direct the complex order of simulation (Baudrillard 1990, 12). Hegelian logic differs from the standard wisdom of harmonious balance. Its point is not equilibrium or a yin/yang balance, but its opposite: 'truth' is located in the excess of exaggeration. The surplus undermines the falsity of a balanced totality (Zizek 1997, 116).

"*Reporting From the Front*" was the title of the 2016 Biennale curated by Alejandro Aravena, who invited each country to share its battles through design. The

mud, bamboo, and brick on view, in addition to the recycled elements, did not visually seduce many of the critics. The discourse sharpened, as some did not agree with the exhibition's apparent architectural saviorism and virtue signaling, and others celebrated the works as a declaration of a new contemporary philosophy. The conclusion of the event was its collapse into its own academic battleground. From the front of Venice, an emerging culture war was reported. Seven years later, the 18th Biennale, "*Laboratory of the Future*," launched its exposition of sociological and environmental issues focusing on decolonization and decarbonization. Its scope of decentering traditional architectural representation and representatives lead to a collection of work with an interdisciplinary character. The exhibition's introverted concerns did not cover the visual presentation; the spectacle of architecture was absent (Harvey 2024). Schumacher, characteristically provocative, assessed the laboratory as a self-annihilation of the discipline (Lloyd 2023).

The shared thread of the aforementioned Biennali is the shifting relationship between the field of architecture and the object in architecture, which has surfaced from the domain's growing politicization and broadening. The result is an idealization of otherness, a politics risking the consumption of its historical subjects, before allowing them to become historically effective (Hal 1996, 179)

The merge of ethical truth and aesthetic appearance has become a common architectural principle. In *Modern Architecture*, Bruno Taut claims: "A building must be beautiful when seen from the outside if it reflects all these qualities. The architect who achieves this task becomes a creator of an ethical and social character" (Taut 1992, 9).

The moralization of buildings implies the splendor of the subject and the poverty of the object. The subject makes history, the subject totalizes the world, individual subject or collective subject... The object's fate is not claimed; it is not intelligible and is only an alienated part of the subject, as an obscene positivization of the void (Baudrillard 1990).

However, it is an illusion to believe that the subject is the aggressor in the game of seduction; rather, it is the matrix of fascination of the object that the subject falls prey to. *Seduction is the supremacy of objects* (Kellner 1989, 157).

Fig.33

Fatal Phenomenology

The *femme fatale* is the subject performing as the object. She is pure appearance, seemingly devoid of agency, which only the subject possesses; the container for the subject's desires and projected meaning. In the seductive process, the subject becomes disempowered, as the *femme fatale*'s strategy is not communication but manipulation, ending the idea of the passive object. The object has an "evil genie" (Baudrillard 1990, 25), triumphant over the subject.

Seduction is not the effect of simple attraction but the redoubled attraction, the challenge. It is fatal in its essence: "I'm not beautiful, I'm worse" said Marie Dorval (Baudrillard 1990, 27).

Fatal strategies are woven into the quantum fabric of the cosmos and thus beyond human control. Its diabolical technique uses the human lack of imagination. "The object may only pretend to obey the laws of physics because it gives so much pleasure to the observer" (Baudrillard 1990, 17).

Their phenomena go past the subject's examination and its autocratic motives.

The turn to the object is growing interest in architecture today, a reaction to the 20th century's manifestos for political action or critical engagement (Gage 2015, 95). The contemporary philosophical movement towards *Object-Oriented Ontology* (OOO) has entered the architectural discourse due to its rejection of offering any solutions to new formalisms or reactionary materialisms.

"To be an object-oriented philosopher," writes philosopher Graham Harman, "what you need to do is hold that individual entities of various scales are the ultimate stuff of the cosmos" (Gage 2015, 95). Harman's work strongly emphasizes on making a case for the object, including its mysteries and power (Gannon 2015, 74). He argues that a grasp of reality can only be neared through illusion (Harman 2012, 51). The replacement of epistemology with aesthetics relieves architecture from its apparent representational duties in tectonic expressions or material additions that allow for a human scale (Wiscombe 2015, 83).

The building does not reject its context; it can simply not be understood and thus serves as a sensual hyper-object.

Fatal Phenomenology aims at a form of *rhetoric* (the art of speaking and writing persuasively) in architecture. In phenomenology, subjectivity is the carrier of meaning. Baudrillard removes the subject and points at the object strategy, which offers to disclose its magic.

Fig.34

It is, therefore, not the epiphany of meaning that concerns the phenomenological analysts but the apophany of the real.

The reduction of meaning, not to meaning.

Seduction allows for this apophatic approach, which is the tradition of rhetorically raising something by denying it or proving god by what he is not.

Baudrillard labels his project as *Raw Phenomenology*. While phenomenology is the study of presencing, raw phenomenology is the phenomenology of absence. His theory first appears to be the antithesis of phenomenology; however, it is not. The sphere of seduction is the sphere of pure appearance; consequently, Baudrillard describes phenomena as they appear. Appearance precedes the order of subjectivity, meaning, reality, and truth (Geniusas 2004).

Cindy Sherman's unfiltered close-up image of an abstracted face (Fig. 33) touches on the object obscenely by pushing to uncover the uncanny real. Its illusionism does not seduce but overwhelmingly abjects (Hal 1996, 149). The seductive filter is the difference between gods and humans, humans and beasts.

"When like couple with like, everything becomes obscene. The necessity of irony, like that of pleasure, is part of the necessity of Evil" (Baudrillard 1990, 108).

Yukio Mishima's story of "*The Golden Pavilion*" (Mishima 1959) offers an extreme portrayal of the seductive, catastrophic object-subject relationship (Fig. 34). Insecure about his appearance, the young protagonist endlessly fantasizes about the structure's beauty, which he has never seen and only heard about. The object exists in the subject's imaginary sphere, unleashing an obsessive yearning for superior beauty. The protagonist's own lack of beauty is in contrast with the architecture's mythical and idealized lure. He burns the idealized pavilion in his Nietzschean strive of overcoming his deficiency.

The murderous end is a desperate attempt of the subject to disempower his object of desire and end its seduction.

The mephistophelian object is catastrophic as it pushes things to their limit. It does not bother with truth or performs a Buddhist surrender to circumstance;

it seduces,
leads away,
and lies.

In its fatality, the object lacking *will* performs a death drive *to power*.

THE VOICE OF SALOME:

AH! I HAVE KISSED THY MOUTH, IOKANAAN, I HAVE KISSED THY MOUTH. THERE WAS A BITTER TASTE ON THY LIPS. WAS IT THE TASTE OF BLOOD? . . . BUT PER CHANCE IT IS THE TASTE OF LOVE. THEY SAY THAT LOVE HATH A BITTER TASTE. . . . BUT, WHAT MATTER? WHAT MATTER? I HAVE KISSED THY MOUTH, IOKANAAN, I HAVE KISSED THY MOUTH.

[A MOONBEAM FALLS ON SALOME, COVERING HER WITH LIGHT.]

HEROD:

[TURNING ROUND AND SEEING SALOME.]

KILL THAT WOMAN!

(WILDE 1967)

Conclusion

Architecture has exhausted itself in its quest to justify its means of practice. It has falsely positioned itself from the sole viewpoint of the subject. To balance this neglect of self, the persistent urge to reach truths and meanings has to be paused.

Humans, bearing the gift of consciousness but not the ability to see the world as it is truly, have relentlessly composed theories that try to make sense of real conditions in relation to themselves.

This quest arises from a castrated position of lack, yearning, and desire.

Like an endless Russian doll, matter absorbs infinite light particles, but its detection can only be finite. Humans, only perceiving a small extract of the whole, have to accept the object's lying appearance.

The architectural tradition of treating buildings as diagrammatic static containers of truthful elements is inherently narcissistic, as sense can only be received in relation to the self. Our lack of access to the other creates a gaping distance, challenging the subject to be seduced.

Seductive architecture must not fall prey to its own theorization by reducing itself to philosophy; rather, it should find new ways of mystifying the object, consequently inviting its inherent seduction of self.

Building seductive is not one style nor one credence; it is only rhetoric. Persuading itself through the means of design, an architecture of seduction argues for greater lies in place of unspectacular attempts towards truth.

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